

SYNTHESIS OF [4-(4-OXO-2 PHENYL-4H-QUINAZOLINE-3-YL)-PHENOXY]-ACETIC ACID-N-(SUBSTITUTED PHENYL)-THIOSEMICARBAZIDES AND THEIR BIOLOGICAL ACTIVITY

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Abstract:- The reaction of [4-(4-oxo-2-phenyl-4H-quinazolin-3-yl)-phenoxy]-acetic acid hydrazide with various phenyl isothiocyanates in isopropyl alcohol gave [4-(4-oxo-2-phenyl-4H-quinazolin-3-yl)-phenoxy]-acetic acid-N-(substituted phenyl)-thiosemicarbazides. The structure of the newly synthesized compounds have confirmed by IR, ¹HNMR and Mass spectra. The compounds have also been screened for their biological activity.

Keywords:- Thiosemicarbazide, IR, Spectral studies, Biological activity.

1. INTRODUCTION

The Chemistry of heterocyclic is an interesting branch in organic chemistry. Thiosemicarbazides derivatives are known to possess antibacterial¹⁻², antifungal³⁻⁵ and herbicidal⁶ activities. Quinazoline derivatives are important compounds in chemistry and pharmacology which include anticancer⁷, anti-inflammatory⁸, anticonvulsant⁹ and antidiuretic¹⁰ activities. These biological data prompted us to synthesize some new quinazoline containing thiosemicarbazide derivatives.

2. EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 General Procedure

Melting points were taken in open capillaries and are uncorrected IR spectra (KBr in cm⁻¹) were recorded on Jasco 410 plus FTIR spectrophotometer. ¹HNMR spectra were recorded on a JEOL 300 MHz FT-NMR spectrophotometer using DMSO-d₆ as solvent and TMS as internal standard (chemical shift in δppm).

The mass spectra of compounds were determined with Shimadzu model no. OP 2010. The element analysis was carried out on a Perkin Elmer C.H.N. analyser and sulphur analysis was obtained by oxygen flask method. The purity of the compounds was monitored by thin layer chromatography. TLC was carried out on pre-coated 0.2mm silica gel₆₀ F₂₅₄ plates.

2.2 General Preparation

1. (4-Acetyl amino-Phenoxy)-acetic acid ethyl ester-(2)

A solution of 4-(hydroxy phenyl)-acetamide (1) 14 gm 0.1 mole) 400 ml N,

N-dimethyl formamide was heated at 70^o-75^oC with ethyl chloroacetate (12.47 ml, 0.10 M) in an oil bath in presence of anhydrous potassium carbonate (12.8 g 0.10 mole).

The reaction mixture was cooled and 1500 ml of cold water was added. The white coloured crystalline solid separated was filtered and washed thoroughly with cold water and then with cold ethanol and finally recrystallised from 99% ethanol, yield 72% m.p. 102^oC, IR (KBr)(cm⁻¹) 3345(NH), 1745 (C=O, ester), 1590, 1510, 1510, 1475 (C=C, aromatic).

2. (4-amino-phenoxy)-acetic acid ethyl ester-(3)

Compound-2, (22.7 g, 0.1 mol) was heated with 35 ml concentrated with hydrochloric acid and 100 ml water for about 2 hours. The clear solution obtained was filtered and neutralization with 35 ml of sodium acetate solution. The compound as white crystalline solid separates on filtration. Yield 73%, m.p. 250^oC, IR (KBr)(cm⁻¹) 3466(NH₂), 1650(C=O), 1560, 1510, 1445(C=C, aromatic).

3. (4-amino- phenoxy)-acetic acid ethyl ester-(4)

Compound-3, (10.58g, 0.05 mol) was suspended in 250 ml ethanol and cooled to 10^oC. The reaction mixture was refluxed for about 2 hours and the product was extracted with 3×25ml of dichloromethane. The dichloromethane layer was washed with 3×20ml of water. The compound-4 obtained on distillation

of dichloromethane at atmospheric pressure was dried in an oven at 40°C and re-crystallised from benzene. Yield 82%, m.p. 60°C, IR(KBr)(cm⁻¹) 3385(NH₂), 1740(C=O ester), 1560, 1511, 1478(C=C, aromatic).

4. [4-(4-oxo-2-phenyl-4H-quinazolin-3-yl)Phenoxy]-acetic acid ethyl ester-(5)

A mixture of 2-phenyl-4H-3,1-benzoxazin-4-one (4.40g 0.020 mol) and (4-aminophenoxy) acetic acid-ethyl ester (4) (4.25g) The reaction mixture was cooled at room temp. and then 100ml of methanol was added slowly. The product 5 separated was filtered, washed with ethanol and crystallized from ethanol.

Yield 85%, m.p. 182°C, IR(KBr)(cm⁻¹) 1735 (C=O ester) 1652(C=O.N), 1608(C=N), 1580, 1546, 1510, 1450(C=C, aromatic). ¹HNMR(DMSO-d₆) δ1.24 (t, 3H, CH₃), 4.2 (q., 2H, CH₂), 4.7 (s, 2H, O.CH₂.C), 6.8-8.7 (m, 13H, ArH), Anal. Calcd. For C₂₄H₂₀N₂O₄ (400): C, 72.00H, 5.00N, 7.00 Found C, 71.98, H 5.04, N., 6.90.

5. [4-(4-oxo-2-Phenyl-4H)-quinazolin-3-yl)-Phenoxy]-acetic acid hydrazide-(6)

Compound 5 (4.5 g 0.01 mol) and 2 ml of 99% hydrazine hydrate in ethanol was refluxed for about 7.5 h. The reaction mixture was then allowed to cool room temp. The separated while coloured solid was filtered, washed with ethanol and crystallized from ethanol.

Yield 82%, m.p. 222°C, IR (KBr)(cm⁻¹) 3318, 3275(NH.NH₂), 1675(C=O amide), 1652(CO.N), 1605(C=N), 1510, 1452(C=C, aromatic), ¹H NMR (DMSO-d₆) δ 4.3 (s, 2H, NH₂) 4.4 (s, 2H, O.CH₂.C), 6.9-8.6 (m, 13H, ArH), 9.3 (s, 1H, NH), Anal. Calcd. for C₂₂H₁₈N₄O₃ (388): C. 68.39, N, 4.66, N. 14.50, Found C. 68.41, H. 4.65, N, 14.52.

6. [4-(4-oxo-2-Phenyl-4H-quinazolin-3-yl)-Phenoxy]-acetic acid -N-(substituted phenyl)-thiosemicarbazides (7a-d):

Compound 6(0.386g. 0.001 mole) was refluxed with various aromatic phenyl isothiocyanates (0.0011 mole) in isopropyl alcohol (40 ml) with continuous stirring over a period of 15 hours. The crystalline solid obtained on cooling the reaction mixture was filtered, washed with

isopropyl alcohol and finally crystallized from ethanol to produce compounds (7a-d).

7. [4-(4-oxo-2-phenyl-4H-quinazolin-3-yl)-phenoxy]-acetic acid -N-phenyl thiosemicarbazide(7a)

Colourless solid, yield 84%, m.p. 195°C, IR (KBr)(cm⁻¹) 3230(NH), 1678(CON), 1662 (CH₂CO), 1600(C=N), 1558, 1508, 1496, 1446 (C=C aromatic), ¹H NMR (DMSO-d₆) δ 4.6 (s, 2H, O, -CH₂C), 6.9-8.6 (m, 18H, ArH), 9.6 (s, 1H, NH), 9.7 (s, 1H, NH), 10.3 (s, 1H, NH); Anal. Calcd. C₂₉H₂₃N₅O₃S (521); C, 66.79; H, 4.41; N, 13.43; S, 6.14; FOUND: C, 66.74; H, 4.38; N, 13.52; S, 6.10.

8. [4-(4-oxo-2-phenyl-4H-quinazolin-3-yl)-phenoxy]-acetic acid-N'-(4-fluorophenyl)-thiosemicarbazide (7b)

Colourless solids, yield 86%, M.P. 200°C; IR (KBr)(cm⁻¹) 3213 (NH), 1697 (CH₂CO), 1683(CO.N), 1602 (C=N), 1585, 1508, 1489 (C=C, aromatic); ¹H NMR (DMSO-d₆) δ4.6 (s, 2H, O.CH₂C), 6.9-8.6 (m, 17H, ArH), 9.6(s, 1H, NH), 9.7(s, 1H, NH), 10.3 (s, 1H, NH); Anal. Calcd. for C₂₉H₂₂FN₅O₃S (539): C, 64.56; H, 4.08; N, 12.77; S, 5.93, Found: C, 64.59; H, 4.11; N, 12.82; S, 6.00.

9. [4-(4-OxO-2-phenyl-4H-quinazolin-3-yl)-phenoxy]-acetic acid-N-(4-nitrophenyl)-thiosemicarbazide (7c)

Pale yellow coloured solid, yield 80%, m.p. 180°C; IR (KBr)(cm⁻¹) 3286 (NH), 1701 (CH₂CO), 1647 (CO.N), 1597(C=N), 1587, 1556, 1508, 1496 (C=C, aromatic); ¹H NMR (DMSO-d₆)δ 4.6 (s, 2H, OCH₂C), 6.9-8.6 (m, 16H, ArH), 9.7 (s, 1H, NH), 10.3 (s, 1H, NH); Anal. Calc. for C₂₉H₂₁N₆O₅S (566): c, 61.48; H, 3.88; N, 14.84; S, 5.65. Found: C, 61.45; H, 4.39; N, 14.82; S, 5.70.

10. [4-(4-oxo-phenyl-4H-quinazolin-3-yl)-phenoxy]-acetic acid-N-(2,4-difluorophenyl)-thiosemicarbazide (7d)

Colourless solid, yield 78%, m.p. 202°C; IR (KBr)(cm⁻¹) 3250 (NH), 1662 (CH₂CO), 1635 (CON), 1600 (C=N), 1583 1558, 1508, 1485 (C=C, aromatic); ¹H NMR (DMSO-d₆)δ 4.6 (s, 2H, OCH₂C), 6.9-8.6 (m, 16H, ArH), 9.7 (s, 1H, NH), 9.8 (s, 1H, NH), 10.3 (s, 1H, NH); Anal. Calc. for

C₂₉H₂₁F₂N₅O₃S (557); C, 62.47; H, 3.77; N, 12.56; S, 5.74; Found: C, 62.51; H, 3.76; N, 12.62; S, 5.78.

3. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

4-hydroxy-phenyl acetamide 1 on electrophilic substitution with ethyl chloroacetate gave (4-acetylaminothenoxy)-acetic acid ethyl ester to which on hydrolysis with aqueous hydrochloric acid gave 4-(amino-phenoxy)-acetic acid 3. This on further esterification with sulphuric acid gave 4-(amino-phenoxy)-acetic acid ethyl ester 4.¹¹

The 2-phenyl-4H-3, 1-benzoxazin-4-yl¹²⁻¹⁶ which was prepared from 2-amino anthranilic acid and benzoyl chloride at 20^o-25^oC in pyridine was allowed to react with 4-(amino-phenoxy)-acetic acid ethyl ester 4 to give [4-(4-oxo-2-phenyl-4H-quinazolin-3-yl)-phenoxy]-acetic acid ethyl ester 5. The structure of compound 5 was established by analytical and -spectral data.

The compound 5 was then condensed with hydrazine hydrate in

ethanol to afford [4-(4-oxo-2-phenyl-4H-quinazolin-3-yl)-phenoxy]-acetic acid hydrazide 6 in good yields. The compound 6 on reaction with various phenyl isothiocyanates in isopropyl alcohol gave [4-(4-oxo-2-phenyl-4H-quinazolin-3-yl)-phenoxy]-acetic acid-N'(substitute phenyl)-thiosemicarbazides (7a-d).

The presence of NH group is confirmed by IR spectra which showed characteristic band at 3300 cm⁻¹ and ¹H NMR signal at 8.96, 9.7 and 10.3 corresponding to O=C .NH .NH C=S .NH protons.

4. BIOLOGICAL ACTIVITY

4.1 Antibacterial Activity

All the newly synthesized compounds (7a-b) were screened in vitro for their antibacterial activities against Staphylococcus aureus, Escherichia coli and Bacillus subtilis by the bich plate technique using concentrations 15µg/ml. nutrient agar was employed as culture media while DMF served as solvent control for antibacterial activity.

4.2 Antifungal Activity

The compounds (7a-d) synthesized were screened for their antifungal activity against Aspergillus niger, Candida albicans and Rhizopus oryzae by paper-disk diffusion method at concentrations of 15µg/ml. Nutrient agar was employed as culture media and DMF was used as solvent control for antifungal activity. The known compounds viz. Ampicillin, Norfloxacin, Penicillin and Griseofulvin were used for comparison purpose. The diameter of zone of inhibition was measured in mm. The antibacterial and antifungal screening data are recorded in Table 1.

Table 1: Biological activity data

Compounds	Zone of inhibition in mm					
	Antibacterial activity			Antifungal activity		
	S. Aureus	E. Coli	B. Subtilis	A. Niger	C. Albicans	C. Neoformans
7a	10	09	10	11	13	14
7b	12	13	15	13	12	13
7c	15	10	16	15	11	16
7d	14	13	11	10	14	10

From the table 1 it can be seen that the compound 7c and 7d show remarkable activity against S. Aureus. Compounds 7b and 7c showed remarkable activity against B. Subtilis. The compound 7c showed good activity against A. Niger and Compounds 7a and 7c show maximum activity against C. Neoformans.

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